

OVERVIEW OF KINETIC PRODUCTION FUNCTIONS FOR AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

Jaborov Elbek Erkin o'g'li

Karshi at the University

Irrigation and Agrotechnology

institutes assistants

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Annotation

The theoretical foundations of the mechanisms for building and forecasting an empirical model using systematic analysis and digital technologies have been improved to ensure macroeconomic sustainability of agricultural production development. Effective use of basic production resources, or in general, the level of utilization of existing potential in ensuring macroeconomic sustainability of agricultural production development is assessed.

Keywords:

Digital technology, empirical model, econometric model, potential, relative model, forecast results, information system, endogenous variables, exogenous variables.

One of the most important tasks in the development of agricultural production is to increase the efficiency of the use of existing potential. But the key issue here is to express the production potential in a single model and determine the efficiency of potential use through it. The process becomes more complicated if the issue is seen on an entire regional scale. Also, the choice of arbitrary variables of the model, i.e., the identification of potential components, poses sufficient problems. In other words, it is possible to develop a model that describes the laws of agriculture, and that the model must include such free variables that these variables represent the value of the individual factors that play a key role in the production process.

We selected the main production resources and, taking into account the possibility of increasing their costs, developed an overview of the kinetic production function, as well as built specific models of this function for the Kashkadarya region. We also found that the Cobb-Douglas-type production function can only be used without any cost increase.

The general view of the kinetic production function for the agricultural production we propose is as follows

$$Y_k = \frac{A_k \cdot Y}{a_0} = A_k \cdot \prod_{j=1}^n x_j^{\alpha_j} \cdot e^{a_j x_j} \quad (4)$$

is represented by equality. In accordance with (4), we used the following model to assess the effectiveness of the use of existing potential in the production of agricultural products in the private sector

$$Y_k = \frac{A_k \cdot Y}{a_0} = A_k \cdot \prod_{j=1}^4 x_j^{\alpha_j} \cdot e^{a_j x_j} \quad (5)$$

Here Y is determined from the following equation

$$\ln(Y) = \ln(a_0) + \sum_{j=1}^4 a_j x_j + \sum_{j=1}^4 \alpha_j \ln(x_j) \quad (6)$$

as well as x_1 - area of agricultural land (thousand hectares); x_2 - average number of employees; x_3 is the annual average value of fixed assets; x_4 - the amount of working capital (billion soums); Y - gross agricultural output (billion soums).

In model (5) - the elasticity of the j-free variable (α_j), - the coefficient (a_j), - the proportionality coefficient, which represents the change (increase or decrease) of the resulting magnitude relative to the amount of this factor for a 1 percent change (increase) of the j-factor. The proportionality coefficient has no meaning (does not participate) in the basic model.

Given the structural structure of the linear equation (6), the x_j resource in its composition comes with its logarithmic value. In practice, if a state of disparity is observed in any of the production resources, in model (6) this resource comes with its logarithmic value. In this case, it is necessary to reduce or increase resource consumption. This can be expressed in the following relationship

$$c = \alpha_j + a_j x_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 4. \quad (7)$$

Figure 2. Algorithm block diagram to solve the problem of assessing the effectiveness of the use of agricultural production potential

If, in (7), it is not equal to zero, the optimal state of the amount of j-resource sufficient for the increase in production volume (Y) is determined by the ratio.

If the product in (7) is zero, a 1 percent increase in the j-resource indicates a direct

percentage increase in Y (which should always be positive).

If it is zero, then a 1 percent increase in j -resource means a direct percentage increase (or decrease) in Y . More precisely, if a negative is found, the increase in the amount of resource is accompanied by a decrease in the efficiency of its use (resource use efficiency is moderately low), a 1% increase in j -resource represents a direct percentage decrease in Y . Also, in the model (5), each resource is involved.

Thus, we can describe an algorithm for solving the problem of assessing the level of efficient use of agricultural production potential (Figure 2). The given algorithm is of linear type, which makes it more understandable. While certain conditions and iterations are observed in the problem-solving process, this is not particularly important because it is a small process performed within each algorithm step. This means that the modeling process is based on a linear algorithm.

References and resources used

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